

**Climate
Change**
Consultation

Report

A Summary of the Response to the Climate Change Consultation

August 1999

Department of the Environment, Transport and the Regions

Department of the Environment, Transport and the Regions
Eland House
Bressenden Place
London SW1E 5DU
Telephone 0171 890 3000
Internet service: <http://www.detr.gov.uk/>

© Crown Copyright 1999

Extracts of this guide may be made for non-commercial in-house use, subject to the source being acknowledged.

Applications for reproduction should be made in writing to The Copyright Unit, Her Majesty's Stationery Office, St Clements House, 1-16 Colegate, Norwich NR3 1BQ.

Further copies of this guide are available from:

Department of the Environment, Transport and the Regions
DETR Free Literature
PO Box No 236
Wetherby
LS23 7NB
Tel: 0870 1226 236
Fax: 0870 1226 237

August 1999 – Product Code 99EP0406

Printed in the UK. Text printed on material containing 75% post-consumer waste and 25% ECF pulp.

Foreword

It is becoming clearer month by month that climate change is one of the greatest environmental threats that we face today and that its consequences will be far reaching. The potential human, social and economic cost of allowing climate change to run its current course could be huge. This was why, last October, we published a consultation paper to stimulate a national debate on how we might meet the UK's legally binding target to cut greenhouse gas emissions by 12.5% below 1990 levels by 2008-2012 and move towards our domestic goal of a 20% cut in CO₂ emissions below 1990 levels by 2010. I am extremely pleased that so many people participated in the consultation and I would personally like to thank all those who took part.

The consultation was only the start of a longer term process to develop a new climate change programme for the UK and this report summarises the initial messages that people wanted us to hear. It shows that businesses, local authorities, the general public and a wide range of other organisations are equally concerned about climate change and that they are pleased that the Government is taking a leading role in the fight to cut emissions. It also tells us that people are keen to do what they can to help the UK meet its targets and that they are full of ideas about what they and the Government can do. We now intend to follow-up these ideas, and to build on the commitment to tackle climate change that clearly exists as we develop the UK programme. The next step will be for us to publish a draft programme for further consultation later in 1999 and I hope that people will be just as enthusiastic about contributing to this ongoing debate.

A handwritten signature in black ink, which appears to be "Gordon Brown". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

Introduction

1. Between 26 October 1998 and 12 February 1999, the Government carried out a major consultation throughout England, Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland on how the UK might meet its climate change targets. We are very grateful to the groups who helped us to arrange seminars during the consultation, to those who provided venues free of charge, and to all those who either went to a seminar or sent in a written response.¹

THE REASON FOR THE CONSULTATION

2. This consultation was the first step in the development of a new climate change programme for the UK. The consultation paper was designed to stimulate a national debate on how the UK might meet its legally binding target under the Kyoto Protocol to cut greenhouse gases by 12.5% by 2008-2012 and move towards the domestic goal of a 20% cut in carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions by 2010. And it did. We sent out over 30,000 copies of the paper to businesses, local authorities, the general public, associations, trade unions, and a whole host of other organisations across the UK. In England, the DETR held eight regional seminars in Hull, Coventry, Plymouth, Nottingham, Bolton, Reading, Durham and Cambridge and invited people to come and talk about the consultation paper and to suggest ideas about what we could all do to cut greenhouse gas emissions. The Trades Union Congress also kindly arranged a conference. DETR ministers went to most of the seminars to hear people's comments. The Scottish Executive (formerly The Scottish Office), in association with the UK Climate Impacts Programme and the Economic and Social Research Council ran two conferences of experts to identify distinctly Scottish issues. The Scottish Office Environment Minister attended both conferences. And in Wales, the Welsh Office held a workshop on climate change impacts at the beginning of 1999 which was attended by their Minister who outlined the issues set out in the consultation paper. We also put the consultation paper on the internet where it was accessed 4,417 times between October and the end of January.
3. In addition to the consultation paper, we published a technical support paper on energy efficient measures in the domestic sector. The paper was available on the website and three workshops were held in London to discuss it during December and January.
4. By the time the consultation closed, a total of 607 written responses had been received – 508 from England, 72 from Scotland, 12 from Wales and 15 from Northern Ireland. There were also six written responses to the technical support paper. All the responses were read and analysed by officials across a number of Government departments and the DETR employed Ecotec – independent consultants – to carry out a detailed, in-depth analysis of a sample of around half the responses. We also made sure that the issues people talked about at the seminars were noted and fed into the analysis. The comments that people made are now being used to help develop the new climate change programme.

¹ The Department of the Environment, Transport and the Regions (DETR), the Scottish Executive (formerly The Scottish Office), the National Assembly for Wales (formerly the Welsh Office) and The Department of Environment for Northern Ireland organised the consultation. The following groups helped to arrange the English regional seminars: the Local Government Association, the Confederation of British Industry, the Trades Union Congress, Friends of the Earth, the Institute of Energy, the Passenger Transport Executive Group and the Government Offices for the Regions.

AIM OF THIS REPORT

5. This report is a factual summary of the subjects that were raised during the consultation. The graphs use information from a database which was assembled by officials at the DETR and they are based on an analysis of all the responses. Members of the public can inspect the written responses by arrangement for six months from the date of this document. They can be seen at:
 - DETR's library, Ashdown House, 123 Victoria Street, London SW1E 6DE, phone 0171 890 3039, for all the responses;
 - the library of the Scottish Executive, Saughton House, Broomhouse Drive, Edinburgh EH11 3XD, phone 0131 244 4552, for responses sent to the Executive;
 - the National Assembly for Wales, Cathays Park, Cardiff, CF10 3NQ, phone 01222 825449, for responses sent to the National Assembly; and
 - the Department of the Environment for Northern Ireland, Environmental Policy Division, 13th Floor, River House, 48 High Street, Belfast BT1 2DR, phone 01232 257351, for responses sent to DoE/NI.

NEXT STEPS

6. The next step is for the Government to publish a draft UK climate change programme towards the end of 1999 for further consultation. We are aiming for the completed programme to be in place in good time for UK ratification of the Kyoto Protocol, which is unlikely to take place before 2001. The Scottish Executive is considering the need for a Scottish response based on devolved policy measures in support of the UK programme. The Department of the Environment for Northern Ireland is assessing how Northern Ireland can contribute to the UK programme. And the National Assembly for Wales will shortly be considering its policy on climate change. At the international level, countries are focussing on implementation of the Kyoto Protocol. The Fourth Conference of the Parties (COP4) in Buenos Aires in November 1998 agreed an Action Plan for taking forward work on a range of key issues, with a view to reaching decisions at COP6 which is due to be held at the end of 2000. The Action Plan covers the Kyoto mechanisms (see paragraph 27 below), compliance with the Protocol and the involvement of developing countries in the process.

Main Messages

7. Our analysis of the responses to the consultation showed that there was agreement on a number of main messages.
 - In general, people were very positive and welcomed the consultation paper as a useful first step in the development of a new UK climate change programme. They agreed that the policy on climate change was heading in the right direction but they also understood that more detailed work would be needed as the programme developed. In particular, people wanted to see more details about the costs, benefits and the level of carbon savings from each option.
 - There was some agreement that taking action to cut greenhouse gas emissions presented business with a great opportunity and that the business sector should continue to take a positive approach to the whole issue. Some people pointed out that if business does not act now, it could lose out to others and be left behind in the global market place.
 - Many people felt that the consultation paper should have said more about what would happen after 2012. If more substantial cuts in emissions will be needed, then planning must begin now.
 - It was widely agreed that all sectors should play a part in helping to meet the UK's climate change targets. A multi-stakeholder approach was needed, but with everyone taking

individual responsibility. People in business were keen to stress that they should not bear an unfair share of the target. Others singled out transport as a sector which deserved special attention, since its emissions were expected to continue rising between 1990 and 2000.

- Local authorities were very positive about the role they could play in helping to cut emissions. They wanted the Government to set the right strategic framework and to give them the right tools to do the job.
- Some people were surprised that the consultation paper did not discuss the need to adapt to the unavoidable impacts of climate change. Businesses in particular realised that they needed to be more aware of the potential effects of climate change on their activities.
- Almost everyone thought that the general public needed to be more aware of climate change and the need to use energy more wisely. They agreed that this was vital for the success of any climate change programme. New social norms and values needed to be created over time and people needed to be given simple, consistent and clear messages.
- There were differing views about the domestic goal to cut CO₂ emissions. People agreed that the technical capacity existed to reduce CO₂ emissions by 20% by 2010, but many businesses were opposed to the goal on cost grounds. They welcomed the Government's promise that no action would be taken which would damage the UK's competitiveness. Environmental groups, some local authorities, the general public and others thought that the UK was right to show leadership by going beyond the Kyoto target.
- Various taxes received a mixed post-bag. For example, the fuel duty escalator had its supporters as well as its fierce detractors. Carbon and energy taxes were supported by some environmental groups and members of the public but businesses were not in favour. There was some agreement among businesses that the Government should give a clear signal about the long term direction of taxation policy and make gradual and predictable changes so that they can plan for future investment.
- Almost everyone who responded thought that there was a great deal of scope for more efficient use of energy, particularly in households and small businesses. People supported setting energy efficiency standards of performance ('EESOPs') for energy utilities, and had lots of other ideas about how energy efficiency might be improved. They also identified barriers which they thought were currently in the way.
- There was much support for renewable energy, although many people thought that the target to deliver 10% of the UK's electricity from renewable sources would be difficult to achieve without changes to the planning system and without more investment.
- Many people, particularly those in Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland, thought that intensive farming methods should be reformed, energy crops should be encouraged and the forests we have should be looked after, and perhaps expanded.
- And finally, people looked to the Government to lead by example.

A Summary of Opinions

OBJECTIVES

8. The consultation paper, *UK climate change programme: consultation paper*, aimed to stimulate a national debate about how the UK might meet its legally binding Kyoto target to cut a basket of six greenhouse gases by 12.5% to below 1990 levels over the period 2008-2012 and move towards the domestic goal of a 20% cut in carbon dioxide (CO₂) below 1990 levels by 2010. It set out a number of different options which could be used to meet the targets and it made a first attempt at assessing the costs and benefits of each option. This section of the report summarises the comments that were made, both in writing and at the seminars. It follows the same format as the consultation paper.

OVERVIEW

9. In general, people agreed that climate change was a serious threat and that the UK should take steps now to reduce its effects. Most people also agreed with the principles set out in the consultation paper, especially the Government's commitment not to take any action that would damage the competitiveness of UK businesses and its aim that all sectors of the economy should play their part. Everyone agreed that we all have a role to play in taking action to cut emissions.
10. There were differing views about the domestic goal to cut CO₂ emissions by 20%. Many environmental groups, some local authorities, members of the public and others thought that the UK was right to show leadership by going beyond the Kyoto target. But businesses were worried that achieving the 20% goal would affect their competitiveness. Quite a few of the respondents pointed out that Kyoto was only the start of the process and that deeper cuts would be needed in the future. They thought therefore that the new programme should look beyond 2012 and identify options for a longer-term strategy. The point was also made that the UK was going to achieve the voluntary Rio target of reducing emissions to 1990 levels by 2000 largely as a result of the so-called 'dash for gas' the switch from coal to gas fired power stations. It was widely agreed that the Kyoto target would be more difficult to meet.
11. Many people were surprised that the consultation paper did not discuss the need to adapt to the unavoidable impacts of climate change. A small number of people dealt exclusively with this issue and said that there was an urgent need for us to put adaptation strategies in place. Businesses also realised that they needed to be more aware of the potential impacts of climate change on their activities.

Energy Supply Industry

FUEL SOURCES

12. Some people were concerned that many of the changes to the energy supply industry mentioned in the consultation paper could not be achieved within the timescale set by the Kyoto Protocol. The coal industry pointed out that they should continue to develop clean coal technology because it could be exported to large developing countries such as India and China who rely heavily on coal and will continue to do so for the foreseeable future. There was a difference of opinion about nuclear energy. The nuclear industry claimed that it was a proven technology which was capable of producing electricity with low carbon emissions. Environmental groups were opposed to any expansion of nuclear energy.

RENEWABLES

13. There was a large amount of support for a greater use of renewable energy.² Some thought that the Non-Fossil Fuel Obligation (NFFO) and Scottish Renewable Orders (SRO) were a good way of helping renewables because they brought the price down. Others thought that major changes would be needed to make them more effective. They felt that a whole package of measures would be necessary to meet the Government's target of producing 10% of the UK's electricity from renewable sources, ideally by 2010. Many people wanted more money for research and development and for demonstration projects. They also

² On 30 March 1999, the Government published a consultation paper, *New and Renewable Energy – Prospects for the 21st Century*. The report identified key issues and challenges which the Government and industry needed to address to achieve its target of producing 10% of UK electricity, cost effectively, as soon as possible.

pointed out that it was not always straightforward to obtain planning permission for renewable projects and this was quoted as the most important constraint on the development of renewable energy in the UK. The following were suggested as possible ways of improving the situation:

- giving better guidance to local authority planning officers;
 - changing planning guidance;
 - making sure that the general public was involved at an early stage in the consultation process; and
 - including renewable energy projects in new developments.
14. Businesses said that they would buy electricity from renewable sources provided it was competitive on price, there was a reliable supply, or if it helped to improve their corporate image. There was general agreement that electricity would not be bought from renewable sources on a large scale without some sort of Government intervention or financial support. However, pressure from customers could help.

ENERGY SERVICES

15. People confirmed that there was potential for energy services packages, including energy efficiency measures, to cut greenhouse gas emissions but they pointed out that the availability, awareness and take-up of energy services by domestic consumers and smaller businesses were still limited. They also believed that energy policy had focused on reducing the price of energy and that not enough attention had been paid to services which helped consumers reduce energy use. The following were also mentioned as being barriers to the wider use of energy services:
- the industry's unwillingness to offer energy efficiency measures on hire purchase terms, when consumers could change their energy supplier at one month's notice;
 - customers were sometimes wary of the value for money of energy services and companies' financial motives; and
 - energy managers did not have a high enough profile within companies, making it difficult for them to gain senior management commitment to reducing energy costs.

Suggested solutions included educating consumers, especially smaller businesses, about the advantages of effective energy management. This could be done via the internet, through trade associations or through programmes managed by the Energy Savings Trust. Many local authorities also wanted powers so that they could become partners in energy service schemes.

COMBINED HEAT AND POWER

16. There was a great deal of enthusiasm for combined heat and power (CHP), where electricity and heat are generated in the same plant. The consultation paper had referred to the Energy Technology Support Unit's (ETSU) analysis of the potential capacity for cost effective CHP, giving a range of between 10-19 MW by 2010 depending on energy prices and other parameters. The top end of this range was felt to be high as not all industries used the mix of electricity

and heat for which CHP was technically suited. But people agreed that the potential – most of which would be in large industrial CHP applications – was considerably higher than the current 4 MW of CHP, and the 2000 target of 5 MW. Many people supported the idea of small scale, community CHP plants. Other suggestions for helping CHP included:

- developing district heating systems financed by private finance or Government grants;
- continued preference for CHP in Government power generation consents;
- early implementation of the Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control (IPPC) Directive; and
- support for demonstration projects.

Business

17. There was some agreement that taking action to cut greenhouse gas emissions presented business with a great opportunity and that the business sector should continue to take a positive approach to the whole issue. Some people also pointed out that if business does not act now, it could lose out to others and be left behind in the global market place.

SCOPE FOR SAVINGS

18. Many people thought that there was great potential for cost effective savings to be made in this area, although some said that the scope was greater in the commercial rather than the industrial sector. Energy-intensive industries claimed that they had already introduced

many energy saving measures for commercial reasons. Some people also pointed out that the incentive to cut energy costs had fallen away since energy prices were currently low and were generally a small percentage of turnover. This has meant that energy efficiency had not received attention from senior management. People went on to say that commitment from business executives was critical to the success of any climate change programme.

19. There was agreement that a mixture of policies was needed to achieve any further cuts in emissions, including voluntary agreements, economic instruments, regulations and incentives. Businesses generally favoured market-based mechanisms because they gave them more flexibility.

ENERGY/CARBON TAX

20. There was a difference of opinion about an energy/carbon tax. Environmental groups and local authorities thought that a tax could help reduce emissions. However, most businesses were concerned that it might affect their competitiveness. Several people said that a tax should be revenue neutral and that it should be offset against other forms of corporate taxation, for example, National Insurance contributions, business taxes etc. Others thought that the revenue from such a tax should be recycled back into industry to help improve energy efficiency.³
21. There was some agreement amongst businesses that the Government should give clear signals about the long term direction of taxation policy and make gradual and predictable changes so that they can plan for the future.

ENVIRONMENTAL REPORTING AND MANAGEMENT

22. Many people, especially environmental groups and businesses, thought that more companies should report publicly on their environmental performance as this might encourage them to invest in energy efficiency. Some also suggested that regular energy audits should be carried out, so that any savings could be included in a company's annual accounts. A number of businesses believed that introducing environmental management systems in their companies could help to stimulate energy savings.⁴

INTEGRATED POLLUTION PREVENTION AND CONTROL (IPPC)

23. There was widespread support for the requirement in the IPPC Directive for companies to use energy efficiently, with most people agreeing that this would act as an important stimulus for better energy efficiency in the sectors covered by the legislation. However, there were some concerns. A number of businesses hoped that the requirements would not be too prescriptive and that their competitiveness would not be affected. They also thought that the relationship between IPPC and emissions trading needed to be clarified.

3 The Chancellor of the Exchequer has since announced plans for a climate change levy on the business use of energy that will be introduced in April 2001. There will be offsetting cuts in employers' National Insurance contributions and additional support for energy efficiency schemes and renewable sources of energy. Energy intensive sectors of industry will also be eligible for a reduced rate of tax providing they agree targets for improving their energy efficiency.

4 In June 1999, the Government published the first guidelines to help companies report on their greenhouse gas emissions. They provide a voluntary standard for measuring and reporting emissions from the full range of company activities including energy use in buildings, freight transport and business travel.

SHARING BEST PRACTICE

24. There was agreement that giving advice and educating businesses about the benefits of energy efficiency could help them to introduce more energy saving measures. The DETR's Energy Efficiency Best Practice Programme was mentioned by a number of people who thought that it was a good way of helping businesses to focus on the benefits of energy efficiency. It was also suggested that businesses themselves could publicise their achievements to encourage others to do the same.

BARRIERS TO BEING ENERGY EFFICIENT

25. People mentioned various barriers which they said affected their ability to be energy efficient. Bids for energy efficiency projects had to compete with bids for other, higher priority projects within the same company. Some people thought that energy efficiency investments had a high capital cost. Others said that there were long payback periods for investment in energy efficiency which made it an unattractive proposition. The current low cost of energy meant that there was little economic incentive to reduce energy use. Some cited a lack of management time, knowledge and overall awareness and many businesses were less inclined to improve, for example, the insulation of their buildings if they rented them.

ENCOURAGING SMALLER BUSINESSES

26. The following ideas were mentioned as ways of helping smaller businesses to improve their energy efficiency.
 - Many thought that the Government should make free or low cost energy audits available, accompanied by free or low cost consultancy advice.
 - Some respondents said that information and advice which gave a clear, consistent message was needed.
 - Some suggested that existing networks, for example, local chambers of commerce, should be used to give out information and advice.
 - Some people stressed that using larger companies could influence smaller ones through the supply chain.

KYOTO MECHANISMS

27. There was a difference of opinion about whether we should use the three Kyoto mechanisms the clean development mechanism, joint implementation and international emissions trading to help meet our targets. These mechanisms allow countries to achieve part of their legally binding commitments by taking action to cut emissions abroad. Environmental groups, some local authorities and members of the public thought that we should not use the Kyoto mechanisms and that we should show developing countries that we were serious about taking action at home to cut emissions. They did, however, accept that the mechanisms would probably be used and they suggested having a limit or cap on the amount of emissions that could be traded. All the businesses who responded were in favour of using the mechanisms. There was some discussion about how the mechanisms should work in practice and how a domestic trading scheme should operate. There was however no clear agreement.⁵

CUTTING EMISSIONS OF HYDROFLUOROCARBONS (HFCs), PERFLUOROCARBONS (PFCs) AND SULPHUR HEXAFLUORIDE (SF₆)

28. There were many suggestions for cutting emissions of HFCs, PFCs and SF₆ including:

- eliminating or reducing emissions at the manufacturing site;
- more research into the development of cost effective alternatives;
- economic instruments to encourage industry to use alternatives, for example, hydrocarbons instead of HFCs;
- more emphasis on recovery and recycling;
- better training of users to reduce leakage;
- emissions trading; and
- better observance of voluntary codes of good practice.

There was some concern about the prospect of banning HFCs, especially from those in the health sector and the refrigeration industry. Most of the people who responded in this issue recommended that 1995, rather than 1990, should be used as the bare year for HFCs, PFCs and SF₆ as the quality of data was better.

5 Work on setting up a domestic carbon emissions trading scheme is now underway. It is hoped that the scheme will be led by business, with the active involvement of and a clear steer from the Government. The CBI and the Advisory Committee on Business and the Environment (ACBE) have already held initial meetings with Ministers and chief executives from interested companies to discuss the design of the scheme.

Transport

29. Many people were concerned that emissions from the transport sector were forecast to grow. They agreed that the policies announced in the integrated transport white paper⁶ should help to improve the situation but they also pointed out that money was needed to introduce many of the initiatives and that some of the changes would inevitably take a long time to happen, for example, the changes in the land use planning system. People also commented on the complexity of some of the figures we used in the paper.

PUBLIC TRANSPORT

30. The integrated transport white paper was warmly welcomed and people hoped that it would bring good quality, reliable and attractive public transport that people could use instead of their cars. In particular, people wanted through-ticketing, better information, quicker door-to-door journey times, as well as better accessibility, cleanliness, etc.

ALTERNATIVE FUELS

31. People thought that, in the short term, using cleaner fuels such as compressed natural gas and liquid petroleum gas could cut emissions. The main barrier to the use of these fuels at the moment is the low number of re-fuelling centres. People also thought that other alternatives could play a part in the future, for example, hydrogen, fuel cells, electric vehicles and bio-fuels such as ethanol.

DEMAND MANAGEMENT AND SPEED LIMITS

32. Some people agreed that road pricing, especially in urban areas, would cut car use. There was, however, concern from some local authorities about the effects on local businesses. There was a similar difference of opinion about workplace parking charges. It was suggested that demand management measures like these would be effective if they were coordinated at a regional level to avoid competition between local areas. Many agreed that 'carrots', for example, better public transport or more facilities for cyclists and pedestrians, would be needed if 'sticks' like road pricing and parking charges were to be effective. They also said that different solutions were needed for urban and rural areas. There was widespread support for the strict enforcement of speed limits.

LOCAL TRANSPORT PLANS

33. People agreed that local transport plans could substantially cut emissions if enough money was given to finance the proposals and if the necessary legislation was put in place to allow road user and workplace parking charges. They said the most important elements of local transport plans were:

⁶ *A new deal for transport: better for everyone*, The Stationery Office, Cm3950

- the creation of safe routes to schools;
- quality partnerships between local authorities and local public transport operators; and
- partnerships between local authorities and businesses.

Some people made the point that local transport plans need to be integrated with the wider land use planning system and with policies from other Government departments. For example, OFSTED inspectors had recently criticised some schools for providing insufficient parking spaces for parents to drop their children off by car. A major employer had also been given a large tax bill for the financial assistance that it has been giving to its staff as part of its green transport plan. It was said that acts like these give out the wrong signals.⁷

FUEL DUTY STRATEGY

34. There was a difference of opinion about the fuel duty escalator – the annual 6% above inflation increase on petrol prices. For example, environmental groups and some academics thought that it was an important way of cutting emissions from transport. Other people, however, questioned the effectiveness and said that the escalator could unfairly affect people living in rural areas.

RAISING AWARENESS

35. Many people thought that the main challenge in the transport sector was winning people's hearts and minds and actually changing their behaviour. They suggested that this could be achieved by giving the general public more information about the effects of their transport choices on climate change, perhaps through a national transport awareness campaign, TV programmes, school packs, the internet, etc. Some people thought that video-conferencing and home working should be more vigorously promoted, especially in the public sector. It was also suggested that little steps could make a big difference, for example, bus drivers switching their engines off while they were waiting in the depot.

PLANNING GUIDANCE

36. There was a widespread view that the land use planning system should give sustainable development a higher priority. Some suggested that no new out-of-town developments should be built. Some thought that better use should be made of existing shopping centres. Others wanted mixed developments with good shops, services and public transport.

⁷ In the Budget in April 1999, the Chancellor announced some changes to transport taxation. A major reform of the company car taxation regime will be introduced, on a revenue neutral basis, in April 2002. Company car drivers will be taxed on a percentage of the car's price varying with the car's carbon dioxide emission rate. The current discounts for business mileage will also be abolished. A reduced rate of Vehicle Excise Duty (VED) of £100 for cars with engines up to 1,100cc will be introduced from 1 June 1999 and from autumn 2000, a system of VED for new cars based on emissions of CO₂ will be introduced. A package of seven tax measures is being introduced to promote non-car commuting, the use of bicycles for business journeys and car-sharing to help the development of green transport plans.

FREIGHT TRANSPORT

37. Several people commented on the fact that freight transport had not been included in the consultation paper and they strongly supported measures that would assist the transfer of freight from road to rail or ship. It was pointed out that emissions from the freight sector were rising because more freight was being moved longer distances. Some thought that 'just-in-time' delivery requirements meant that there was unnecessary empty running and congestion.

AVIATION AND SHIPPING

38. Most people said they believed that aviation fuel should be taxed. An airline operator suggested that emissions from aircraft could be cut by better air traffic management, navigation and surveillance systems, and engine design. The industry also claimed that, as fuel was a major cost, they were already doing what they could to improve fuel efficiency. Few people mentioned emissions from ships, although one public sector group pointed out that taxing marine fuel could cause organisational problems.

Domestic

TARGETS

39. A wide range of people believe that a 10 million tonnes of carbon (MtC) cut in emissions from the domestic sector by 2010 was a realistic target. Some did say that it was too optimistic but others thought that it was ultimately achievable. Local authorities said that the target could only be met under certain conditions, for example, if enough money was available and supporting policies were put in place. Others said that Government and industry should make it easier for people to 'go green' by providing cheap energy efficient products and services.

BETTER ENERGY EFFICIENCY

40. Many people saw the following measures as being cost effective:
- cavity wall insulation;
 - loft insulation;
 - draughtproofing;
 - hot water tank lagging;
 - efficient heating systems, in particular gas condensing boilers;
 - better use of heating controls;
 - energy efficient lighting, particularly compact fluorescent lighting;
 - energy efficient appliances; and
 - replacement double glazing using low emissivity glass.

BUILDING REGULATIONS

41. There was a lot of support for changing the building regulations to include tighter energy efficiency standards. People also thought that the regulations should apply to existing houses, particularly when they were being renovated. Some people wanted energy efficient technologies, such as solar heating, to be used more widely in the construction of houses.

HOUSEHOLD ENERGY EFFICIENCY SURVEYS

42. There was widespread support for including details of a property's energy efficiency in the surveys that are carried out when people buy and sell homes. There was a difference of opinion about whether the seller should be responsible for this or whether it should be part of the mortgage survey.

RAISING AWARENESS

43. Almost everyone thought that the general public needed to be more aware of climate change and the need to use energy more wisely. They agreed that this was vital for the success of any climate change programme. New social norms and values needed to be created over time and people needed simple, consistent and clear messages. The message could be sent out via the media, the internet, schools, church groups, health visitors, etc. Mentioning that people could save money would help to get the message across. Several people thought that climate change should be included in the National Curriculum. Others thought it would help if there was one common source of authoritative information about all aspects of climate change which could be in the form of a website run by the Government.

TAXATION

44. Some people suggested that changing the tax regime for energy and for energy efficient products would be an important, cost effective way of getting people to alter their consumption habits. There was a difference of opinion about taxation of domestic fuel. Some were concerned about the effect of higher taxes on those with low incomes. Others thought that the gradual increase of fuel prices would stimulate householders to invest in energy efficiency. Rebates could be given to the poor to make sure that they were not adversely affected.

MINIMUM STANDARDS FOR ELECTRICAL APPLIANCES AND ENERGY LABELLING

45. Most people agreed that minimum energy efficiency standards for electrical appliances were a good way of helping to cut emissions. They also felt that the standards should be supported by labels on appliances which gave details of the product's energy efficiency and running costs. Some people suggested that inefficient products should be removed from the marketplace.

BARRIERS

46. People identified the following as barriers preventing them from being more energy efficient:
- the cost of energy saving products, insulation, etc and the perceived lack of an immediate return or tangible benefit;
 - a lack of public awareness about energy saving measures;
 - short term thinking;
 - the current low cost of energy which has meant that investment in energy efficiency has a low priority;
 - landlord/tenant issues, for example, if a landlord invested in energy saving measures, it would be the tenant who benefited from reduced fuel bills;
 - the generally short time people spend, or think they are going to spend, in a particular property;

- the home energy efficiency scheme (HEES) only allowed occupants to apply for one HEES grant. Many early beneficiaries of the scheme had been provided with draughtproofing but were now not eligible to apply for cavity wall insulation. Local authorities in particular wanted this rule scrapped;⁸ and
- local authorities also saw the bidding process for the Home Energy Conservation Act (HECA) grants as a barrier and wanted more money put into the scheme.

OTHER AREAS

47. There was general support for the energy efficiency standards of performance (EESOP) scheme. Many people thought that it should be extended beyond 2000 and that it should include the gas sector. Several groups, including health and environmental groups, welcomed our commitment to promoting better domestic energy efficiency because people's health would benefit from having warmer homes.⁹

TECHNICAL SUPPORT PAPER ON ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN THE DOMESTIC SECTOR

48. As we mentioned in paragraph three of this report, the Government also published a technical paper which discussed and invited comment on the leading possible measures for energy saving in the domestic sector, the scale of savings available and the costs and benefits, including health benefits. Three workshops were held to discuss the paper and we received useful comments. Other possible measures were identified and there were detailed comments on the critique and calculations in the technical paper. People also confirmed the assessment that savings of up to 4 MtC a year by 2008-12 from the domestic sector were achievable. Other specific points made at the workshops are covered elsewhere in this report.

8 The Government has since announced proposals for a radical change to a 'New HEES' scheme, in which more extensive energy saving measures, including central heating for pensioners, are available to eligible householders regardless of whether they have previously received a HEES grant.

9 Since the consultation paper was published, the Government has announced that the proposed Utility Reform Bill is to include provision for Government to set EESOPs for electricity and gas suppliers. In the meantime, the regulator plans to consult shortly on whether he should continue his electricity SOP scheme when the present scheme finishes in April 2000 and whether a gas scheme should be initiated.

Agriculture, Forestry and Land Use

49. Some people said that the level of emissions from the agriculture sector was still uncertain, especially the levels of methane and nitrous oxide. Several environmental groups and members of the public wanted to see a shift towards more organic farming, which they thought would reduce emissions of nitrous oxide. Many people were critical of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) because they believed that it created incentives to intensify agricultural production. They hoped that it would be reformed.

EMISSIONS FROM LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION AND NITROGEN APPLICATION

50. There were some academics who thought that changes to the diet of cattle would substantially cut the emissions they produce. There was also some support for the use of anaerobic (without oxygen) digestion of farm wastes as a way of converting waste into fuel. Local authorities and environmental groups wanted to see more integrated farming systems, minimum tilling and farmers following agricultural codes of good practice. There was general support for more research and development into this area.

BIOMASS

51. There was widespread support for the use of energy crops and many people were optimistic about their potential. They believed that well managed biomass schemes were good for biodiversity and rural employment and made relatively little use of fertilisers and mechanised equipment. People also wanted more short rotation coppice (SRC) projects which used willow or poplar. Some thought that the current CAP regime would prevent the number of new projects predicted in the consultation paper from being started. Some farmers were also unwilling to plant SRC because it committed their land for at least five years and the grants

available were lower than for cereals. The agricultural industry suggested a number of ways to improve the financial yields from SRC:

- changes to CAP to create a brand new energy crops regime supporting annual as well as woody energy crops;
- more research and development;
- changes to the woodland grants scheme; and
- future NFFO tranches with bands targeted at biomass.

SINKS AND AFFORESTATION

52. Many people supported the expansion of 'broad leaved native species' forests which they believed could soak up large amounts of carbon. However, others said that the amount of carbon absorbed would be small in comparison to emissions in the air. They agreed that more emphasis should be given to cutting emissions rather than increasing carbon sinks.

Public Sector

TARGETS

53. Local authorities were generally very positive about the role they could play in helping to cut emissions. They wanted the Government to set the right strategic framework and to give them the right tools to do the job. They pointed out that not having enough money to invest could limit the amount of savings that they could achieve. They also mentioned that it was difficult to get information about energy use in their areas from supply companies.

This was making it difficult for them to gather baseline data and to measure whether their policies were succeeding.

54. A significant number of local authorities already had action in hand to be more energy efficient. Some of them set out the amount of energy savings they were planning to make. The levels ranged from 10% to 30% over the next four or five years. Many people believed that the public sector, including local authorities, should set a good example for others and they pointed out that, often, public sector buildings were very visible and could showcase new environmental and energy efficient technologies.

MANAGING THE PUBLIC ESTATE

55. The following were mentioned as ways in which the public sector could improve the energy efficiency of its own estate:
 - taking part in environmental management systems;
 - adopting green procurement plans covering, for example, appliances, computers, fleet vehicles, etc;
 - buying green electricity;
 - investing in CHP – especially for high profile buildings such as the Houses of Parliament;
 - hiring energy managers, especially in schools;
 - recycling waste;
 - pioneering green transport plans;
 - publishing annual energy use data;
 - empowering local authorities to participate in CHP schemes and energy service companies; and
 - allowing local authorities to use money raised from the landfill tax to fund energy efficiency projects.
56. Some people said that devolving energy budgets to head teachers had reduced action on energy efficiency in most schools. This was because head teachers did not have the time or the money to think about energy efficiency and often did not have the expertise to be efficient customers. Others suggested that there could be an accreditation scheme for schools, for example, a green plaque for an energy efficient building.

OTHER IDEAS

57. Many local authorities thought that climate change objectives should be included in the Best Value programme. They recommended that each local authority should have an environmental coordinator, perhaps as part of their local agenda 21 strategies. The coordinator would have some sort of strategic control over the local authorities' policies and programmes and could make them consistent with sustainable development. Local authorities pointed out that they have a key role in influencing businesses' waste management policies. They admitted that they could do more to encourage businesses in their area to improve their environmental performance. There was also a call for planning guidance to cover climate change in more detail.

A UK Consultation

58. The following section provides a summary of the issues mentioned in responses to the Scottish Executive, the National Assembly for Wales and the Department of the Environment for Northern Ireland. As we said in the consultation paper, the legally binding Kyoto target is for the UK as a whole and a UK-wide programme will need to be developed to deliver it. Some of the policies needed to deliver the UK's climate change targets will be the responsibility of the Scottish Parliament and the Welsh and Northern Irish Assemblies, for example, promotion of renewable energy, local transport plans and local awareness campaigns. Other policies will be reserved for the UK Government, for example, on all forms of taxation, energy efficiency standards of performance (EESOPS) and setting the national speed limit. The devolved administrations will therefore have an important contribution to make in the development and delivery of a UK-wide climate change programme. The Scottish Executive is also considering the need for a Scottish response based on devolved policy measures to compliment the UK programme. The Department of the Environment for Northern Ireland is assessing how Northern Ireland can contribute to the UK programme. And the National Assembly for Wales will shortly be considering its policy on climate change.

A Scottish perspective

GENERAL

59. Seventy two responses were received from groups and individuals in Scotland. In general, the consultation document was well received. The vast majority of people recognised the need to do something to tackle the threats posed by climate change. They agreed that the task ahead had been properly assessed and they pointed out that action was required in all sectors.
60. They saw the need to increase people's awareness of, for example, energy efficiency as a key issue, arguing that if people were made aware of the savings they could make at home, the idea would become ingrained and be transferred to the workplace. People expressed disappointment that the current 'Are you doing your bit' campaign had not covered Scotland.

ENERGY SUPPLY

61. There was widespread support for an increase in renewable energy in Scotland. A number of people mentioned Scotland's suitability for renewable energy from wind, waves, tides and biomass. Some people particularly favoured local renewable projects which had the added bonus of promoting rural development. Others recognised that it was important to select the right sites in order to protect Scotland's landscape and biodiversity. They felt there was a need therefore for planning policies which addressed the issue and sought to resolve the potential conflict. There was strong support for a clear commitment to further development of CHP. Given the current fuel mix in Scotland, clarity on the future role of nuclear power was seen as essential.

BUSINESS

62. Improvements in energy efficiency were seen as the most important business sector issue. IPPC was seen to play a key role. There was a call for the introduction of energy audits and for these to be included in annual reports. Many people thought that different approaches were needed for different sized companies. Most stressed that competitiveness in Scotland should not be adversely affected by measures to tackle climate change. Some people said that businesses were discouraged from investing in energy efficiency because they were worried about losing competitiveness and they were not knowledgeable enough. It was important that the Government and the enterprise agencies sent out good quality information.
63. There was a difference of opinion about the Kyoto mechanisms. Most supported them playing some role, although there was an underlying feeling that they should not allow affluent nations to duck their domestic responsibilities. Those who supported use of the mechanisms differed about how they should work. On one side, some thought that only CO₂ should be included in any trading scheme – at least initially. The other side argued that any trading scheme should be comprehensive and include all six greenhouse gases.

TRANSPORT

64. There was widespread support for integrated transport and a belief that real alternatives to car use needed Government support. People thought that community-based solutions backed by money and regulations were important.
65. The one distinctly Scottish issue that cropped up regularly was the need to provide support for remote areas, where people rely on cars and said that they were being harder hit by the fuel duty escalator. The escalator produced a wide range of views. Some supported it, others opposed it, while a number offered ideas on how it might be changed. These included:
- a different rate for rural areas;
 - linking a uniform but lower rate to other measures such as road pricing or congestion charging; and
 - reallocating money raised to projects which promoted sustainable development.
66. Other measures that received broad support were:
- fuel consumption labelling, better fuel efficiency and moves to reduce CO₂ emissions from cars;
 - encouragement for developing alternative fuels;
 - initiatives to reduce speeding; and
 - the publication by the then Scottish Office of the draft *National Planning Policy Guideline and Planning Advice Note on Transport and Planning* (final versions published April 1999).

DOMESTIC SECTOR

67. Many people thought that the Scottish building regulations should be strengthened to require better energy efficiency. A reduction in VAT on energy saving materials and installations was also widely seen as important. An improved energy efficiency standards of performance (EESOP) scheme received a positive response. A few people supported energy efficiency ratings for housing, although there was a difference of opinion about whether it should apply to all housing or only to new homes. Implementation of the Home Energy Conservation Act (HECA) was seen as having the potential to deliver energy efficiency improvements and cuts in CO₂, although some would like to see more money provided. The 'market transformation strategy' won support and some sought an improvement to include minimum energy efficiency standards for electrical appliances. Respondents welcomed the 'warm deal' initiative.

AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND LAND USE

68. A number of people considered this sector was of particular importance to Scotland. The possible further reforestation of Scottish lowlands and retention of peatlands to act as carbon sinks; the fact that three-quarters of Scotland's land area was agricultural; and the potential for diversification into biomass/energy crops were all seen as offering the new Scottish Parliament the opportunity to consider distinctive policies.

PUBLIC SECTOR

69. There was general support for the Government leading by example, for instance through improved energy efficiency in the Government estate and for public sector CO₂ reduction targets. There was also a call for all parts of the public sector to be involved, in particular, for local authorities to adopt local agenda 21 strategies and for the NHS to develop energy efficient health care strategies.

A Welsh perspective

GENERAL REACTION

70. The National Assembly for Wales received 12 responses. There was a general welcome for our commitment to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and for the promise that we would not introduce measures that will damage competitiveness or bring unacceptable social costs. Some questioned how the climate change targets would be equitably spread across the UK.

ENERGY SUPPLY INDUSTRY

71. Most supported a greater role for renewables and thought that energy conservation should be the main priority for energy policy. Many believed that renewables could form an integral part of a diverse energy supply industry, provided there was not an over-reliance on wind energy.

AGRICULTURE

72. Most of the respondents based in Wales raised points about this section of the consultation paper. They agreed that it was difficult both to quantify the current position and to anticipate future agricultural activity. Many thought that there should be more investment in the research and development of energy crops. They felt that the energy crop sector could be supported by a policy to encourage the creation of new markets and to stimulate domestic and small scale industrial combined heat and power (CHP) systems. It was felt that the next Non-Fossil Fuel Obligation (NFFO) should target biomass, although the scale of its use would have an effect on the landscape. A trade union claimed that integrated farm management would lead to more efficient use of fertilisers. Tree planting schemes also received some support.

TRANSPORT

73. People supported the integrated transport policy. Some thought, however, that the fuel duty escalator was too blunt an instrument to reduce demand, particularly in rural areas where there was often little or no alternative to using a car. They suggested several other measures which they thought might be more effective. These included:
- compulsory fuel consumption labelling;
 - changes to VED so that those who owned less fuel efficient cars paid more;
 - lowering speed limits; and
 - congestion charging during peak hours.

Most believed that a 'carrot and stick' approach was needed to encourage people to use public transport. The link between land use planning and transport also needed to be strengthened.

BUSINESS

74. People agreed that there was significant scope for cost effective energy savings in the business sector. Most suggested that emphasising the financial benefits would be the best way of encouraging businesses to be more energy efficient. Many thought that incentives were needed for small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) and that expertise was needed to carry out environmental and financial audits.

DOMESTIC

75. A housing group supported the idea of a carbon tax on domestic fuel, provided the money raised was re-invested in better housing. Some believed that building techniques could be improved. One local authority suggested that solar water heating should be promoted by encouraging house builders to include it in every development.

A Northern Irish perspective

GENERAL REACTION

76. There was widespread support for the consultation paper in the 15 responses that were received in Northern Ireland. People accepted the need to do something about climate change and, in most respects, supported the overall approach. People also made the point that climate change was an issue on which the Government was expected to take the lead and set a good example.
77. Most held the view that considerable work was needed to educate the general public and to explain to the business and public sectors that action was not only necessary for climate change reasons but that it would be cost effective and good business practice in the longer term. A majority agreed that changing people's behaviour, for example, getting them to use public transport rather than their cars, would be very difficult.

RENEWABLE ENERGY

78. There was broad support for the development of renewable energy sources and a number of people highlighted Northern Ireland's good conditions for growing willow.

FINANCIAL INCENTIVES/MEASUREMENT

79. Respondents agreed that some form of financial incentive would be helpful and made a number of suggestions as to the form this might take. A number also supported statutory measures. In general, setting targets and standards was preferred to measuring relative performance.

TRANSPORT

80. The main issue raised in this area was the need to create efficient and cost effective transport systems. This appeared to be particularly relevant to Northern Ireland where there was excessive reliance on the car.

AGRICULTURE

81. As was to be expected given agriculture's importance to Northern Ireland's economy, a number of people were interested in changes to agricultural practices. They called for intensive farming methods to be reduced. There was also support for more forestry to create carbon sinks.

REGIONAL APPROACH

82. Several people wanted the Government to give special attention to a regional approach to meeting the UK's climate change targets, which would take account of relevant factors. For example, there was currently an over-reliance on fossil fuels in Northern Ireland and emission targets should not simply be set on a pro-rata population basis.

Conclusion

83. This consultation played an extremely valuable part in the development of a new climate change strategy for the UK. The results have been widely circulated to all the Government departments, divisions and devolved administrations who are helping to produce the programme, and we are enormously grateful to all those who took part. The next step is for the Government to publish a draft UK climate change programme for further consultation and for the devolved administrations to agree what action they will take in devolved policy areas. The completed climate change programme will be in place in good time for UK ratification of the Kyoto Protocol.